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Academic Stress and Suicidal Ideations/Tendencies Among Undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State

¹Dr. (Mrs.) GEORGE, Kennedy Margaret & ²DOUEYI-FIDERIKUMO, Juliana

^{1&2}Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling,
Faculty of Education

Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

¹Email: Margaret.kennedy@ust.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

The study correlated academic stress and suicidal ideations/tendencies among undergraduates in public Universities in Rivers State. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 1,031 of 300 level students from the Department of Educational Psychology/Guidance and Counseling versus Department of Adult Education of three public universities in Rivers State. Sample size of the study was 420 of 300 level students from the department under study. Proportionate sampling technique was used in selecting the sample size of the study. A self-structured instruments titled: “Academic Stress Questionnaires” (ASQ) and a standardized test “Suicidal Ideation/Tendencies Scale” (SI/TS)” for year three students were used for data collection. Face and content validation of the instruments were determined by an expert in Counselling Psychology and another in Measurement and Evaluation. Cronbach Alpha Method was used to establish the reliability coefficients of 0.78; 0.73; 0.79; for the three clusters of Academic Stress Questionnaires. Test-retest method was used to establish the reliability coefficient of 0.92 for the Suicidal Ideation/Tendencies Scale. Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation (r) was used to answer the research questions, while the t-transformation method was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Results showed that all the variables of academic stress (academic frustration, academic conflicts and academic anxieties) had negative but significant relationship with suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in public Universities in Rivers State. It was recommended among others that counselors should help students to develop frustration tolerance to enable them bear or withstand the pressure when encountering setbacks; students should be encouraged to foster a positive and respectful environment, encourage open communication, among others.

Keywords: academic stress, suicidal ideations/tendencies, public Universities, undergraduates

INTRODUCTION

Suicide is death caused by injuring oneself with the intent to die. A suicide attempt is when someone harms themselves with any intent to end their life, but they do not die as a result of their actions. Suicidal ideation refers to thoughts, fantasies, or contemplation of suicide (Caltabiano, 2002). It can range from fleeting thoughts to more persistent and detailed plans. Suicidal ideation is a serious concern and should be taken seriously. It is often associated with underlying mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, or other psychiatric conditions.

Although it appears that there is no universally accepted definition of suicidal ideation but according to Harmer, Lee, Duong and Saadabadi (2023), suicidal ideation (SI), is often called suicidal thoughts or ideas. In a broad term suicidal ideation is used to describe a range of contemplations, wishes, and preoccupations with death and suicide.

Studies have shown that the occurrence of suicide attempt is common among the adolescents and early adulthood (18-35) who are likely to be in schools. This suggests that stress from academics could have been strongly linked to suicide ideation among students. Stress has become part of students' academic life due to the various internal and external expectations placed upon their shoulders. Adolescents are particularly vulnerable to the problems associated with academic stress as transitions occur at an individual and social levels. Uganda, Botswana, Kenya, Zambia, and Nigeria have high prevalence of suicidal ideation among young people (Swahn, Bossarte & Elimam, 2010). These youths within "transitory-into-productive" age(s), are seen to be moving from tertiary institutions into the uncertain world of markets in the developing (and in some Western) worlds (Okechuwu, Ogba, Nwifo, Ogba, Onyekachi & Nwanosike, 2022) Stress has become part of students' academic life due to the various internal and external expectations placed upon their shoulders. Adolescents are particularly vulnerable to the problems associated with academic stress as transitions occur at an individual and social levels (Reddy, Rajan & Thattil, 2018). The only task students were expected to undertake was to study and studying was never perceived as stressful. What proved to be stressful was the expectations parents had for their children, which in turn grew into larger burdens that these children could not carry anymore (Reddy, Rajan & Thattil, 2018).

There are various kinds of academic stress that constitute students' displeasure, depression which results to suicide ideation. Academic frustration is an aspect of academic stress that creates a negative emotional experience among learners. Academic frustration (AF) is defined as a negative psychological emotion experienced by students when they are unable to deal with frustration in their learning process (Ballmann in Wu, Huang, Fu & Zhang, 2023). AF can negatively impact students' interest and enthusiasm in their academic activities, causing them to feel isolated due to their perceived failures, thereby further lowering their personal achievement motivation (Neff et al., in Wu, Huang, Fu & Zhang, 2023). Nonetheless, academic frustration in academic activities may enhance students' learning effect in the short term, however the feeling of frustration nevertheless is detrimental on the long-term learning effect. When a student sits for one exam and keeps failing could result to academic frustration in a long run. According to Yin Tong & Huang (2020), the role of stressful life events such as academic frustration in suicidal ideation, attempts and completed suicides had been a critical area of study in the epidemiology of mental disorders. Also, Ogba, Nwifo, Ogba, Udofia and Chiejina (2020) has it that lack of effective coping strategy when academic frustration sets in for a student could lead to suicide ideation.

Academic conflict happens when disagreement occur between students and teachers, due to the lack of understanding of the teacher's explanation, due to arbitrary grades and divergence in the evaluation criteria, lack of didactic material, discrimination, disinterest in the study material, and because the students are ears (Valente, Lourenço & Németh, 2020). In turn, conflicts between students can arise due to misunderstandings, fights, the rivalry between groups, discrimination, bullying, use of spaces and assets, dating, sexual harassment, loss or damage of school assets, diverse elections, travel, and parties. According to Ajibola and Agunbiade (2022) findings from the qualitative component also considered undergraduates that have academic challenges, engage in substance abuse, and have parents with marital problems to be prone to suicidal ideation. Suicidal ideation among these young people could be embedded in their network of conflicts within the academic spheres, which consequently leads to stress.

Academic Frustration

Academic frustration (AF) is defined as a negative psychological emotion experienced by students when they are unable to deal with frustration in their learning process (Ballmann, Helmer, BergBeckhoff, Dalgaard, Jervelund & Busse, 2022). AF can negatively impact students' interest and enthusiasm in their academic activities, causing them to feel isolated due to their perceived failures, thereby further lowering

their personal achievement motivation (Neff, Hsieh & Dejitterat, 2005). Although AF is a negative emotional experience, it may sometimes lead to positive outcomes. For example, negative emotional experiences can have an amplification function whereby individuals become more motivated to address their own problems with purpose, which is conducive to targeted problem solving (Mather, Clewett, Sakaki & Harley, 2015). Nonetheless, confusion and frustration in academic activities may enhance students' learning effect in the short term, however the feeling of frustration nevertheless is detrimental on the long-term learning effect (Dycord-Liu,

Pataranutaporn, Ocumpaugh & Baker, 2013). In other words, while AF may sometimes be helpful, it does appear to harm study outcomes in the long run.

Thus far, little research has directly investigated specifically students' AF. Instead, studies have focused primarily on some of the leading factors that might cause AF, such as academic failure or level of frustration tolerance. For example, Perry, Hladkyj, Pekrun, Clifton and Chipperfield, (2005) found that students' academic failure is intimately related to their perceived academic control. Those with high academic control pay little attention to academic failure, which leads to little AF. Harrington (2005) found that students with different levels of frustration tolerance might adopt different strategies to deal with stress during the learning process to relieve frustration. Several studies have pointed out that anti-frustration ability (AFA) is a crucial factor causing negative academic emotions, e.g., academic frustration (Yang, Li, Nian, Xu, & He, 2021).

The concept of AFA may be derived from frustration tolerance (Yang & He, 2018). While frustration tolerance described one's ability to bear or withstand the pressure when encountering setbacks, AFA emphasizes the ability to not only endure frustration but to grow with frustration, and take action against frustration (Yang & He, 2018). Wang, Wang and Liu (2006) have argued that people with high resilience, that is, those who possess high AFA, tend to experience more positive emotion.

When in moments of frustration, individuals with high AFA are able to employ different strategies such as self-deprecation or humor to produce more positive feelings, alleviate stress, and adapt to the environment (Block & Kremen, 2014) Dialectical behavior therapy (DBT) contends that the tolerance of pain, in this case frustration tolerance, plays a central role in one's ability to adapt to undesirable behaviors and alleviate frustration (Simons & Gaher, 2005). Frustration tolerance is the reflection of students' view and attitude toward AF. However, each person adapts to frustration differently. People with strong frustration tolerance can withstand stressors and manage to find their way through periods of learning difficulties (Li, Yu, Gao, Tang, Liao & Zhang, 2019). As studies indicate that AFA might play an important role in college students' ability to deal with their AF, we thus proposed our first hypothesis: AFA directly influences students' AF (H1). Theoretically, AFA can trigger positive emotion which is initially constructive and thus broaden an individual's attention and cognition (Fredrickson, 2013). This facilitates one's ability to enrich their persistent resources. In this process, core competence (CC, or key competence) is regarded as a kind of crucial persistent resource that might work on AFA's influence upon AF. CC is the essential character and crucial competencies that enable students to adapt to the changing world (Wiek, Withycombe & Redman, 2011).

Core competence facilitates the development of one's creativity, self-directedness, and self-motivation (Xin, Jiang, Lin, Shi & Liu, 2016). It also helps students to deal with various challenges, including those they face in their academic activities. Scholars tend to regard CC as an important part of the fundamental dynamics that facilitate a student's ability to adapt to the future world (Lin, 2016). According to Huang, Zuo, Mo, Liu, Xin and Lin (2016), CC is multi-layered, involving culture related literacy (e.g., language, mathematics, science), self-related literacy (e.g., learning skills, mental health, self-management), and society-related literacy (e.g., social responsibility, value, beliefs). Guerra and Bradshaw (2008) have pointed out that youth should develop five core competencies including (1) a positive sense of self, (2) self-control, (3) decision-making skills, (4) a moral system of belief, and (5) prosocial connectedness. The cultivation of undergraduates' core qualities is a key requirement of the connotative development of higher education, as well as an important way to carry out the fundamental task of establishing morality

and cultivating talents and developing socialist builders and successors with all-round development of morality, intelligence, physique, and esthetics (Lin, 2016).

With the ongoing evolution of educational resources, both conceptually and tangibly, undergraduates are being pushed to perpetually improve their individual comprehensive abilities, to achieve an increased comprehensive development in their studies and personal life. A study conducted in Chinese high schools found that students' AFA was significantly positively related to CC (Li, Yu, Xie, Chen, Zhao, & Liang, 2020). Xing (2016) showed that AFA can impact students' CC development, and CC, in turn, helps students deal with difficulties in their academic activities. Based on these findings, we proposed our second hypothesis: CC plays a mediating role in students' AFA's influence on their AF (H2).

Coping style (CS) is defined as one's cognitive and behavioral efforts utilized to help one adapt to their environment (Lazarus, 2019). Depending on its impact on one's mind and body, CS can be both positive and negative. Positive CS are problem-centered, that is, the individual tries to solve practical problems, while negative CS are emotion-centered, that is, individuals reduce their negative emotions by using coping strategies such as avoidance and denial (Huang, Zuo, Mo, Liu, Xin & Lin, 2016). Regarding the theory of CS, contextualism holds that one's CS can vary across different situations (Furtado, Tran, Currie & Preyde, 2016).

For example, in the context of academic difficulties, the CS that one adopts will depend on their evaluation of controllable events and the resources they can access to manage stress (Furtado et al., 2016). Positive or adaptive strategies decrease the amount of stress one perceives and experiences, while negative or maladaptive strategies diminish symptoms of stress but without addressing the real problem or disorder. When employing a positive CS, individuals are able to mobilize more psychological resources, including CC (Matud, 2004).

Li et al. (2020) found that CC was closely related to positive CS: individual with high CC tended to employ a positive CS during moments of difficulty. Okechukwu, Ogba, Nwifo, Ogba, Onyekachi and Nwanosike (2022) showed that those who employ a positive CS are better able to deal with their AF. Moreover, a positive CS enables people to experience happiness and pride in their learning, both of which can increase their academic motivation and interest while decreasing their AF (Fitzgibbon & Murphy, 2022). Based on these findings, we proposed our third hypothesis:

CS can be viewed as a moderator in CC's relationship with AF (H3).

Academic Conflict

Academic conflict and suicidal ideation are pressing concerns in educational institutions. Academic conflict refers to disagreements, tensions, or disputes that arise among students, teachers, administrators, or other stakeholders. These conflicts can hinder learning, undermine relationships, and impact overall academic performance (Sahay, 2014).

Types of Academic Conflict

Hawton and Pirkis (2017) outlined the following as types of academic conflict:

1. Intrapersonal Conflict: Inner struggles students face regarding academic goals, motivation, or self-doubt.
2. Interpersonal Conflict: Conflicts between students, teachers, or administrators, such as disagreements, misunderstandings, or communication breakdowns.
3. Group Conflict: Conflicts within groups or teams, often due to differing opinions, roles, or expectations.
4. Institutional Conflict: Conflicts between students and the institution, such as disputes over policies, procedures, or resources.

Causes of Academic Conflict

The following are causes of academic conflict

1. Communication Breakdowns
2. Cultural or Social Differences

3. Academic Pressure and Stress
4. Differing Expectations
5. Personality Clashes
6. Resource Competition
7. Grading Disputes
8. Plagiarism or Academic Integrity Issues
9. Bullying or Harassment
10. Institutional Policies or Procedures (Hawton & Pirkis, 2017).

Effects of Academic Conflict

The following are the effects of academic conflicts according to Arun and Chavan (2014).

1. Emotional Distress
2. Decreased Motivation
3. Poor Academic Performance
4. Strained Relationships
5. Increased Stress and Anxiety
6. Decreased Job Satisfaction (for educators)
7. Negative Impact on Reputation
8. Loss of Productivity
9. Increased Dropout Rates
10. Decreased Overall Well-being

Resolution Strategies

The following are the possible resolution strategies to academic conflict

1. Intrapersonal Conflict (self-reflection and goal-setting, seeking counseling or mentoring, developing time management skills).
2. Interpersonal Conflict (active listening and open communication, conflict resolution training, mediation or arbitration, seeking support from authorities).
3. Group Conflict (team-building activities, clarifying roles and expectations, encouraging diverse perspectives, establishing ground rules).
4. Institutional Conflict (reviewing and revising policies, providing support services, fostering open communication channels, encouraging student feedback).
5. General Strategies (stay calm and objective, identify and address underlying issues, seek common ground, foster a positive and respectful environment, encourage open communication) (Arun & Chavan, 2014).

According to Gill (2017), academic conflict and suicidal ideation are critical concerns that require proactive measures. By understanding the connection, identifying risk factors, and implementing prevention strategies, educational institutions can promote a supportive environment and reduce the risk of suicidal ideation among students.

Academic Anxiety

Academic anxiety refers to the feelings of worry, tension, or dread that are associated with academic settings or tasks. This could be exams, assignments, subjects (math, reading, or science), social pressures related to schoolwork (parents, peers), or merely feeling uneasy about studying or working in groups in class (Abdollah, Ali, Khodabakhsh, Hediye, Alireza & Pilevarzadeh, 2014).

Types of Academic Anxiety

According to Abdollah et al (2014), academic anxiety can be caused by many different sources that are specific to each person. Consequently, the symptoms of academic anxiety may include many different types. There are four facets of academic anxiety: physiological, cognitive, behavioral, and social. Not every learner will exhibit symptoms from all of these categories. For example, it is possible that someone

may experience physiological and cognitive symptoms without ever experiencing any behavioral symptoms. Learning to identify the differences between the symptoms of academic anxiety can help to determine what management techniques work best to manage your individual anxiety.

Physiological Symptoms

According Agnew (2022), physiological symptoms of anxiety are physical symptoms that are felt in the body. In his opinion, academic anxiety can often cause parts of the body to have a nervous or fearful reaction. These symptoms can include:

1. A fluttering, nervous sensation in the stomach (“butterflies”)
2. Nausea
3. Elevated heart rate
4. Fidgeting, feeling “antsy”
5. Headaches, dizziness
6. Nervous sweating
7. Shortness of breath
8. Muscle tension, difficulty relaxing

One of the most effective ways to reduce these physical manifestations of anxiety is to practice relaxation techniques. If anxiety is causing a fear response in the body that interferes with the ability to focus, then learners can prioritize calming the body to manage these responses. Relaxation techniques can include practicing mindfulness, other meditation techniques, or muscle relaxation exercises (Allred, Granger & Hogstromthe, 2013).

Cognitive Symptoms

Aqeel, Mohamed, Abdul and Roslee (2014) are of the view that cognitive symptoms of academic anxiety involve unhelpful thoughts that interfere with performance. Symptoms in this facet of anxiety don't manifest in the body, but in the way a student thinks. A student experiencing this has worries that prevent them from being able to focus on schoolwork. According to Aqeel et al (2014), some examples are as follows:

1. Thoughts stray from the content of study toward worry over performance (cognitive distraction).
2. Inability to maintain attention/stay on task (attentional control).
3. Intrusive thoughts impact ability to remember/process learning (cognitive overload).
4. Trouble accessing the right memories or applying appropriate knowledge (retrieval errors/barriers).
5. Memories are blocked from retrieval while testing or studying occurs only in limited conditions (anxiety blockage).
6. Negative internal self-talk impacts motivation and performance ex. “I can't do this; I'm never going to pass.”

Fortunately, relaxation techniques are also an effective method to manage cognitive symptoms. This is because relaxation techniques help to calm both the body and the mind. Reframing the anxiety, setting proper goals, and fostering skills and abilities vital to self-regulated learning can also be effective in combating academic anxiety (Brand, & Sehoonheim-Klein, 2009). Time management skills, organization, and study habits help to reduce the stress and worry associated with schoolwork by helping the student feel more competent, motivated, and prepared. Mindfulness is another great tool for helping students conquer intrusive thoughts. Mindfulness training is a type of meditation that directs attention from unhelpful cognitions to the present environment. Engaging in these exercises can help to lessen issues in attentional focus and keep students “in the moment” during studying or exams (Brezo, Paris, Tremblay, Vitaro & Hebert, 2015).

Behavioral Symptoms

According to Chioqueta, & Stiles, (2011), behavioral symptoms of anxiety manifest in a student's habits and behavior. An academically anxious person may take behavioral measures to avoid situations that evoke those feelings of worry. This can occur in several ways:

1. Avoidance or procrastination of anxiety-inducing task.

2. Intentionally putting low effort into task due to fear of failure (perfectionistic avoidance).
3. Working on an unrelated (not anxiety-inducing) task.
4. Giving up or saying “I don’t know” instead of persevering through anxiety-inducing task Along with relaxation and reframing techniques, an effective intervention to reduce task avoidance would be to restructure the student’s environment to make it more conducive to learning. Self regulated learning techniques (preparedness, organization, etc.) aid this in addition to setting aside consistent study time, using a planner, and setting up a dedicated space to study.

Social Symptoms

Cole, Protinsky and Cross (2015) argued that social academic anxiety isn’t established as a universally agreed-upon type of anxiety. However, some researchers believe instead that it is better described as a cause of academic anxiety. This is also not the same as Social Anxiety Disorder.

Devi and Prakash (2015), are of the opinion that social Anxiety Disorder is a type of general anxiety disorder and must be diagnosed by a professional. Social academic anxiety, in contrast, is limited to academic situations and can be experienced in varying degrees by varying students. Social academic anxiety involves the fear of a negative reaction from other people (peers, parents, teachers, etc.) after poor academic performance. Students who feel social academic anxiety may be motivated by important people in their lives to perform well in school, and fear of not meeting these expectations can cause avoidant behaviors or feelings of dread or worry (Devi & Prakash, 2015). These students may be especially sensitive to embarrassment in a school environment.

Improving Social Academic Anxiety

According to Cole et al (2014), students can learn to be aware of automatic negative thought patterns and counteract them with positive ideas, such as “I will be okay, I can do this” and “Yes, this test is important, but it is just one grade in this class.” Again, educators and parents might be able to ease some of this social anxiety by reframing the testing mentality and reassuring their students that, while they should take school seriously, their academic performance doesn’t lessen their worth as a person. Relieving some of the threat that comes with exams by encouraging a growth-mindset (“It’s okay to make mistakes as long as we learn from them.”) and creating a calm and secure academic environment can help students to avoid the fear of negative reactions from others.

Here is a resource for educators about how to talk to anxious students, and here is advice for parents about how to talk to your children about schoolwork and tests (Ezeobi, 2017). Academic anxiety comes in a variety of forms: physiological (physical), cognitive (thoughts), behavioral, and social. In order to effectively manage these symptoms, we have to remember that academic anxiety manifests differently from student to student. Selecting techniques to manage this anxiety should be approached from an equally individualized perspective.

Fortunately, many techniques exist to help relieve and prevent this anxiety. Students can explore a combination of relaxation techniques, self-regulated learning habits, environment restructuring, and positive reframing techniques among many other tools to help find a management system that works for them (Ezeobi, 2017).

Statement of the Problem

Suicidal ideation/tendencies is complex; it is an irrational desire to die. Suicide effects are tragic and felt long after the individual has taken his own life. A person who dies by suicide leaves behind a tangled confusion of family members and friend who try to make sense of a senseless and a purposeless act. Hence, suicidal thought among students is associated with several psychosocial indicators for well-being including: depression, loneliness, guilt, grief, anxiety, substance use, poverty, bullying, mood disturbance, feelings of sadness, despair and discouragement, resulting from personal loss and tragedy, poor relationship quality with parents and low social support and thus when perplexed adolescents may see suicide as last option.

Students can experience stress from family discord at home as well as having difficulties with academic pressure and peer relationships at school. In January 2019, a final year student of University of Port

Harcourt committed Suicide over poor grades. Another of such tragic events was a news report by Punch Newspapers of a OND 2 student of Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnics, Port Harcourt that also committed suicide after posting several items indicative of suicidal ideation on social media “*Now I put the phone down to do some actual studying; Some days I feel like a King; other days I wish for death, need a new life, this one is broken, sometimes I feel like I'm fading away*”. This started after he had failed courses and was billed to repeat. To the best of the knowledge of the researcher after an extensive internet search, there is a dearth of published studies on the relationship between academic stress and suicidal ideation among undergraduates in Rivers State Universities. To make matters worse, neither a national suicide prevention strategy nor official suicide statistics exists in Rivers State. Because of the lack of information on suicidal behavior in Nigeria and in Rivers State Universities, suicidal scientists and other stakeholders exploit opportunities to gather information on suicidal behavior, motivated by the premise that additional knowledge of the nature and patterns of suicidal behavior will increase understanding of the issue and lead to the design and implementation of culturally appropriate and effective predictions. Thus, the absence of data in suicide ideation is a great obstruction to the designing, developing and implementing preventative strategies. Given this gap, this study intends to correlate academic stress variables (academic frustration, academic conflicts, academic anxieties, academic pressure, parental high expectancy, poor students counselling) and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to correlate academic stress and suicidal ideations/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the relationship between academic frustration and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State;
2. determine the relationship between academic conflicts and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State;
3. ascertain the relationship between academic anxieties and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State;

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between academic frustration and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between academic conflicts and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between academic anxieties and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between academic frustration and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between academic conflicts and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between academic anxieties and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the correlational research design. The area of the study is public universities in Rivers State, which are: University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State. Rivers State is located in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. The population of the study comprises 300 level undergraduate students from the department of Educational Psychology/Guidance and Counseling versus department of Adult Education in the three public

Universities in Rivers State. That is, University of Port Harcourt (363 students from the department of Educational Psychology/Guidance and Counseling) Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (377 students from the department of Educational Psychology/Guidance and Counseling) and Rivers State University (RSU 291 students from the department of Adult Education), which is made up of 1,031 students. (RSU, IAUE & UNIPORT Matriculation Bulletin, 2021). The sample size of the study was 420 300 level undergraduate students from the Department of Educational Psychology/Guidance and Counseling versus department of Adult Education of the 3 public universities under study (RSU 117, IAUOE 153, UNIPORT 150). The 300 level students will be used as the sample of the study because they are in usually conscious of having extra year and the grade they are graduating with. The Taro Yamene's sample size formula was used to arrive at the sample of 397, but the researcher purposely increased the number by 23 which gave the sample size of 420 for better representation of the target population. Two instruments developed by the researcher with the titled: "Academic Stress Questionnaires" (ASQ) and "Suicidal Ideation/Tendencies Scale" (SI/TS) were used for data collection. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation coefficient was used to obtain the reliability index, hence the reliability coefficient of 0.92 were obtained with the aid of the SPSS version 24. The research questions were answered with Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis, while the t-transformation method was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between academic frustration and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Analysis of Relationship between Academic Frustration and Suicidal Ideation/Tendencies among Undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State

Variable	N	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum XY$	r-value	Remarks
		$\sum Y$	$\sum Y^2$			
Academic Frustration (X)	416	1271	4011	5644	-0.34	Negative
Suicidal Ideation/T. (Y)	416	1911	11259			

Source: Field Data, 2024.

Data in Table1 shows the analysis of the relationship between academic frustration and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State. Results in Table 1 shows that the r-value = -0.34. The negative value of r (-0.34) indicates that the relationship between academic frustration and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Rivers State Universities is negative, which implies that there is a negative relationship between academic frustration and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State. This result could be because most students feel pressure from others (parents, teachers, peers) to perform well academically.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between academic conflicts and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Analysis of Relationship between Academic Conflicts and Suicidal Ideation/Tendencies among Undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State

Variable	N	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum XY$	r-value	Remarks
		$\sum Y$	$\sum Y^2$			
Academic Conflict (X)	416	1261	3917			
Suicidal Ideation/T. (Y)	416	1911	11259	5563	-0.47	Negative

Source: Field Data, 2024.

Table 2 presents the relationship between academic conflicts and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State. Results in Table 2 shows that the correlation coefficient value (r-value) between academic conflicts and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Rivers State Universities is -0.47. The negative r-value (-0.47) shows that the relationship between academic conflicts and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State is negative. Hence, academic conflicts relate negatively with suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State. This result could be because most students struggle with self-doubt about their academic abilities.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between academic anxieties and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Analysis of Relationship between Academic Anxieties and Suicidal Ideation/Tendencies among Undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State

Variable	N	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum XY$	r-value	Remarks
		$\sum Y$	$\sum Y^2$			
Academic Anxieties (X)	416	1244	3832			
Suicidal Ideation/T. (Y)	416	1911	11259	5443	-0.52	Negative

Source: Field Data, 2024.

Table 3 presents the analysis of the relationship between academic anxieties and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in in Public Universities in Rivers State. With the negative correlation coefficient (r) value of -0.52, it can be concluded that there is a negative relationship between academic anxieties and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State. This finding could be because of the obvious fact that students experience anxiety about making academic decisions, and the feeling of uncertainty about achieving their academic goals.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between academic frustration and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State.

Table 4: T transformation on Relationship between Academic Frustration and Suicidal Ideation/Tendencies among Undergraduate Students in Public Universities in Rivers State

Variable	N	$\sum X$	df	r-value	t-trans	t-crit	α	Decision
		$\sum Y$						
Academic Frustration (X)	416	1271	414	-0.34	-6.55	1.96	0.05	Ho Rejected
Suicidal Ideation/T. (Y)	416	1911						

Source: Field Data, 2024.

Table 4 shows that at 0.05 level of significance and degree of freedom (df) = 414, r-value = 0.34, t-trans (t-transformation) = -6.55 and t-critical (t-crit) = 1.96. Since the t-trans value (-6.55 > t-critical value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant relationship between academic frustration and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State” was rejected. It was therefore concluded that there is a negative significant relationship between academic frustration and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State. This implies that academic frustration is a factor that results to suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between academic conflicts and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State.

Table 5: T transformation on Relationship between Academic Conflict and Suicidal Ideation/Tendencies among Undergraduate Students in Public Universities in Rivers State

Variable	N	$\sum X$	df	r-value	t-trans	t-crit	α	Decision
		$\sum Y$						
Academic Conflict (X)	416	1261	414	-0.47	-8.65	1.96	0.05	Ho Rejected
Suicidal Ideation/T. (Y)	416	1911						

Source: Field Data, 2024.

Results in Table 5 revealed that at 0.05 level of significance and degree of freedom (df) of 414, r = -0.47, t-trans value = -8.65 and t-critical value = 1.96. Since at 0.05 level of significance and degree of freedom (df) of 414, the t-trans value (-8.65) > t-critical value (1.96), the null hypothesis that “there is no significant relationship between academic conflicts and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State” was therefore rejected. Hence, it was deduced that there is a negative significant relationship between academic conflicts and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State. This implies that academic conflicts are indices of suicidal ideation/tendencies.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between academic anxieties and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State.

Table 6: T transformation on Relationship between Academic Anxieties and Suicidal Ideation/Tendencies among Undergraduate Students in Public Universities in Rivers State

Variable	N	ΣX	df	r-value	t-trans	t-crit	α	Decision
		ΣY						
Academic anxieties (X)	416	1244	414	-0.52	-9.39	1.96	0.05	Ho Rejected
Suicidal ideation/T. (Y)	416	1911						

Source: Field Data, 2024.

Results in Table 6 show that at 0.05 level of significance and degree of freedom (df) of 414, $r = -0.52$, $t\text{-trans} = -9.39$ and $t\text{-critical value} = 1.96$. Since the $t\text{-trans}$ value of $-9.39 > t\text{-critical value}$ of 1.96 at 0.05 significance level and degree of freedom (df) of 414, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant relationship between academic anxieties and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State” was therefore rejected. Hence, there is a negative significant relationship between academic anxieties and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State. The implication of this finding is that academic anxieties triggers suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduate students.

Summary of Findings

The following are the summary of findings of the study:

1. There is a negative significant relationship between academic frustration and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State.
2. There is a negative significant relationship between academic conflicts and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State.
3. There is a negative significant relationship between academic anxieties and suicidal ideation/tendencies among undergraduates in Public Universities in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusion drawn, the following recommendations were made:

1. Counselors should help students to develop frustration tolerance to enable them bear or withstand the pressure when encountering setbacks.
2. Students should be encouraged to foster a positive and respectful environment, encourage open communication.
3. Educational institutions should provide a supportive environment and reduce the risk of academic anxieties among students.

REFERENCES

- Abdollah, S., Ali, F., Khodabakhsh, A., Hediye, S.M., Alireza, N. & Pilevarzadeh, M. (2014). Personality Factors underlying suicidal behaviour among military youth. *Iran Red Crescent Medical Journal*, 16(4),126-132.
- Agnew, R. (2022). Synnomie to Anomie: A macro sociological Formulation. The Legacy of anomie theory. *Advances in Criminology Theory*, 6(1), 271-83.
- Ajibola A.O., & Agunbiade, O.M., (2022) Suicide Ideation and Its Correlates Among University
- Allred, A., Granger, M. & Hogstromthe, T. (2013). *The relationship between academic achievements, personality type and stress in college students*. Eukaryon, 9, Lake Forest College.

- Aqeel, K., Mohamed, S.M., Abdul, R.H. & Roslee, A. (2014). Influence of psychological factors on suicide ideation among Malaysian and Indian adolescents. *Social and Behavioural Science*, 14(3), 341-351.
- Arun, P. & Chavan, S. (2014). Stress and suicidal ideas in adolescent students in India. *Indian Journal of Medical Sciences*, 63 (7), 281-287.
- Ballmann, J., Helmer, S.M., Berg-Beckhoff, G., Dalgaard G.J., Jervelund, S.S. & Busse, H. (2022). Is lower trust in COVID-19 regulations associated with academic frustration? A comparison between Danish and German university students. *Int. J. Environmental Research in Public Health*, 19, 17-48. Beijing: Beijing Normal University Publishing Group.
- Block, J. & Kremen, A.M. (2014). IQ and ego-resiliency: conceptual and empirical connections and separateness. *Journal Persona-Social Psychology*. 70, 349-361.
- Brand, H., & Sehoonheim-Klein, M. (2009). Is the OSCE more stressful? Examination anxiety and its consequences in different assessment methods in dental education. *European Journal of Dental Education*, 1(3), 147-153.
- Brezo, J., Paris, J., Tremblay, R., Vitaro, F., & Hebert, M. (2015). Personality traits as correlates of suicide attempts and suicide ideation in young adults. *Psychology of Medicine*, 36(2), 191-202.
- Chioqueta, A.P. & Stiles, T.C. (2011). The relationship between psychological buffers, hopelessness and suicidal ideation. *Crisis*, 28(2), 67-73.
- Cole, D.E., Protinsky, H.O. & Cross, L.H. (2015). An Empirical Investigation of Adolescent Suicidal Ideation. *Adolescence*, 27(8), 813-818.
- Devi, S.N. & Prakash, N.R. (2015). Life Skills Assessment Among Undergraduate Students. *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*. 7(3), 3127-3138.
- Ezeobi, C. (2017). Rising cases of Suicide. This day newspaper. April 3, 2017. <https://www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2017/04/03/rising-cases-of-suicide>.
- Fitzgibbon, K. & Murphy, K.D. (2022). Coping strategies of healthcare professional students for stress incurred during their studies: a literature review. *Journal of Mental Health*, 1-12.
- Fredrickson, B.L. (2013). Positive emotions broaden and build. *Advanced Experimental Social Psychology*. 47, 1-53.
- Furtado, J., Tran, A., Currie, V., & Preyde, M. (2016). Exploration of coping strategies of youth accessing residential and day treatment programs. *Contemp. Fam. Therapy*. 38, 108-118.
- Guerra, N.G. & Bradshaw, C.P. (2008). "Linking the prevention of problem behaviors and positive youth development: Core competencies for positive youth development and risk prevention" in *Core competencies to prevent problem behaviors and promote positive youth development: New directions for child and adolescent development*. Vol. 122, 1-17.
- Harmer, B., Lee, S., Duong, T.V.H. & Saadabadi, A. (2023). *Suicidal Ideation*. StatPearls Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing.
- Hawton, K. & Pirkis, J. (2017). Suicide is a complex problem that requires a range of prevention initiatives and methods of evaluation. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 2(10), 381-393.
- Huang, S.L., Zuo, H., Mo, L., Liu, X., Xin, T. & Lin, C.D. (2016). International analysis of core competencies studies for student development. *Journal of Chinese Social Education*, 06, 8-14.
- Lazarus, R.S. (2019). Coping theory and research: past, present, and future. *Psychosom, Med*, 55, 234-247.
- Li, Q., Yu, K., Gao, D. Y., Tang, C. X., Liao, X. W., & Zhang, X. D. (2019). College students' antifrustration mental ability and dependence on academic frustration: the intermediary function of positive psychological quality. *Chinese Journal of Health Psychology*. 07, 1077-1084.
- Li, Q., Yu, K., Xie, J.Y., Chen, Y.C., Zhao, X.Y. & Liang, C.X. (2020). Higher vocational college students' anti-frustration psychological ability and dependence on academic frustration: the intermediary function of core competency and coping style. *Chinese Journal of Health Psychology*. 06, 918-924.
- Lin, C. (2016). *Investigation on the Core Literacy of Students' Development in the 21st Century*.

- Mather, M., Clewett, D., Sakaki, M., & Harley, C.W. (2015). Norepinephrine ignites local hotspots of neuronal excitation: how arousal amplifies selectivity in perception and memory. *Behavioral Science*, 39, 200-212.
- Matud, M.P. (2004). Gender differences in stress and coping styles. *Pers. Individual Differences*. 37, 1401-1415.
- Neff, K.D., Hsieh, Y P. & Dejjitterat, K. (2005). Self-compassion, achievement goals, and coping
- Ogba, K.U., Nwufu, I.J., Ogba, I.M., Udofia, F.T. & Chiejina, C.N. (2020). Academic Stress, Coping and Resilience as Predictors of Suicidal Ideation Among Adolescents. *African Journal of Human Development and Lifespan (AJHDL)*, 2, 159-185.
- Okechukwu, F. O., Ogba, K. T., Nwufu, J. I., Ogba, M. O., Onyekachi, B. N., Nwanosike, C. I., et al. (2022). Academic stress and suicidal ideation: moderating roles of coping style and resilience. *BMC Psychiatry*, 22, 1-12,
- Perry, R.P., Hladkyj, S., Pekrun, R.H., Clifton, R.A. & Chipperfield, J.G. (2005). Perceived academic control and failure in college students: a three-year study of scholastic attainment. *Research of Higher Education*, 46, 535-569.
- Reddy, K. J., Rajan M. K., & Thattil, A., (2018). Academic Stress and its Sources Among University Students. *Biomedical and Pharmacology Journal*, 11, 531- 537.
- Sahay, M. (2014). Academic stress and Suicidal tendency. *Golden Research Thoughts Impact Factor*, 3(11), 524-555.
- Simons, J.S. & Gaher, R.M. (2005). The distress tolerance scale: development and validation of a self-report measure. *Motivation of Emotion*. 29, 83-102.
- Swahn M, Bossarte R, Elimam DM, et al (2010). Prevalence and correlates of suicidal ideation and physical fighting: a comparison between students in Botswana, Kenya, Uganda, Zambia and the USA. *International Journal of Public Health*, 2010, 2:195-206.
- Valente, S., Lourenço, S.S. & Németh, Z. (2020). *School Conflicts: Causes and Management Strategies in Classroom Relationships*. IntechOpen.
- Wang, Y.M., Wang, H.L. & Liu, Y.H. (2006). The nature and function of positive emotions. *Journal Capital Normal University*, 01, 119-122.
- Wiek, A., Withycombe, L. & Redman, C.L. (2011). Key competencies in sustainability: a reference framework for academic program development. *Sustainable Science*, 6, 203-218.
- with academic failure. *Self-Identity*, 4, 263-287.
- Wu M, Huang H, Fu Y & Zhang, X. (2023) The effect of anti-frustration ability on academic frustration among Chinese undergraduates: A moderated mediating model. *Front. Psychology*. 14, 103-190.
- Xin, T., Jiang, Y., Lin, C.D., Shi, B.G. & Liu, X. (2016). On the connotation characteristics and frame orientation of students' developing core competencies. *Journal of Chinese Social Education*, 6, 28-37.
- Yang, X. & He, H. (2018). Developing a scale to measure undergraduates' anti-frustration ability. *Social Behavioral Personality*, 46, 633-640.
- Yang, X., Li, X., Nian, D., Xu, J. & He, H. (2021). Development and psychometric analysis of the anti-frustration ability scale for primary and secondary school students. *Curriculum Psychology*, 41, 8271-8279.
- Yin, Y., Tong, J., Huang, J. (2020). Suicidal ideation, suicide attempts, and neurocognitive dysfunction among patients with first-episode. *Biomedical and Pharmacology Journal*, 11, 531- 537.